

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

***BULLETIN OF* FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF DIFFERENT CLINICAL FORMS OF VIRAL HEPATITIS A DISEASE

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Resume. Changes in TNF- α and HGF levels were identified in HAV infection, demonstrating a relationship between inflammatory and regenerative processes. An increase in TNF- α levels confirms its role as a mediator of inflammation, while elevated HGF levels reflect the response to hepatocyte damage and promote liver regeneration by enhancing hepatocyte proliferation. Higher HGF levels were associated with greater liver injury and an increased need for active regeneration.

Keywords: viral hepatitis, immune system, liver, cachexin, growth factor, cytokines, imbalance.

ИММУН ТИЗИМИНИ ВИРУСЛИ ГЕПАТИТ А КАСАЛЛИГИНИНГ ТУРЛИ КЛИНИК ШАКЛЛАРИ ПАТОГЕНЕЗИДАГИ АҲАМИЯТИ

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Резюме. ВГАда TNF- α ва HGF даражаларидаги ўзгаришлар аниқланди, бу эса яллиғланиш ва регенерация жараёнлари ўртасидаги ўзаро боғлиқликни кўрсатади. TNF- α даражасининг ошиши унинг яллиғланиш медиатори сифатидаги ролини тасдиқлайди, HGF даражасининг ортиши эса гепатоцитлар зарарланишига жавоб реакциясини акс эттириб, уларнинг пролиферациясини тезлаштириши орқали жигар тикланишига хизмат қилади. HGF даражасининг юқорилиги жигар шикастланишининг оғирлиги ва фаол регенерацияга бўлган эҳтиёж билан боғлиқлиги аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: вирусли гепатит, иммун тизим, жигар, кахексин, ўсиш омилли, цитокинлар, дисбаланс.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИММУННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ФОРМ ВИРУСНОГО ГЕПАТИТА А.

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Резюме. При ВГА выявлены изменения уровней TNF- α и HGF, что свидетельствует о взаимосвязи между воспалительными и регенераторными процессами. Повышение уровня TNF- α подтверждает его роль как медиатора воспаления, тогда как увеличение уровня HGF отражает ответ на повреждение гепатоцитов и способствует регенерации печени за счёт усиления пролиферации гепатоцитов. Более высокие уровни HGF ассоциированы с более выраженным повреждением печени и необходимостью активной регенерации.

Ключевые слова: вирусный гепатит, иммунная система, печень, кахексин, фактор роста, цитокины, дисбаланс.

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Relevance of the problem: Millions of cases of hepatitis A virus (HAV) infection are reported each year, with high rates in developing countries [1,2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), hepatitis A virus (HAV) caused 11,000 deaths in 2015 and 7,314 deaths in 2016, accounting for 0.8% and 0.5% of all deaths from viral hepatitis in those years, respectively [2]. Although AHA often causes mild disease, in some cases the infection can lead to acute liver failure and ultimately death. An important aspect of studying the clinical course of AHA and its association with different degrees of severity is that the disease is characterized by a wide spectrum of symptoms, ranging from mild to severe [11]. These differences are explained by both individual patient characteristics and various factors that regulate inflammatory processes and recovery in liver tissues [3].

The clinical course of the disease directly depends on the level of activity of the body's protective mechanisms involved in fighting viral infection and restoring damaged cells [16]. Depending on the severity of the disease, the inflammatory process may be minimally symptomatic or cause pronounced clinical manifestations. Immunological mechanisms of viral hepatitis A play a major role in determining the clinical course of the disease [10,15]. In almost all cases of acute viral hepatitis A, the immune response to HAV is successful, eliminating the virus without long-term persistence. However, HAV infection in adults often leads to severe liver damage through immunopathological mechanisms and is sometimes complicated by fulminant hepatic failure [4,5].

The hepatotropic virus activates the immune system, triggering the body's defense mechanisms. The immune response involves a wide range of cellular and molecular components, including the production of specific cytokines by immune and liver cells [12,14]. The immune response to HAV is robust and highly effective in clearing the virus, usually resulting in an acute onset of illness and often prompting spontaneous recovery [6,8].

The purpose of the study. To study the role of the immune system in the pathogenesis of various clinical forms of viral hepatitis A, paying special attention to immunological markers, inflammation, and liver regeneration mechanisms, as well as assessing their relationship to the severity of the disease and clinical consequences.

Materials and methods. 89 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of viral hepatitis A were included in the study. All patients were divided into groups according to the severity of VGA: group 1 included 35 patients with mild symptoms, group 2 included 33 patients with moderate symptoms, and group 3 included 25 patients with severe symptoms. The control group consisted of 21 practically healthy individuals. Patients included in the study were 19-25 years old.

Immunological tests of the study participants were conducted in the Immunoregulation Laboratory of the Institute of Human Immunology and Genomics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Serum concentrations of tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF α) and hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) were determined using solid-phase immunoassay systems from VECTOR-BEST (Russia) and Cusabio Biotech (China) according to the manufacturer's recommendations.

Statistical analysis of the obtained data was carried out using the computer program "Statistica 6.0". The data were analyzed using simple statistical approaches and the results are presented as follows: sample mean (M) and standard error (m); median (Me), which represents the central tendency, and upper and lower quartiles, i.e., the distribution of the indicator among 50% of patients (Q1-Q3), where Q1 is the 25% percentile, Me is the 50% percentile, and Q3 is the 75% percentile. The difference in the mean values of the compared indicators (p) was estimated using the Student's test (t).

Research results and discussion. Immunological studies included determination of serum TNF α and HGF levels before treatment.

The presented Table 1 shows the changes in serum levels of TNF- α and HGF in patients with different degrees of severity of ACS compared to a control group of practically healthy individuals.

TNF- α is an important pro-inflammatory cytokine that plays a key role in the body's immune response. It is synthesized mainly by macrophages, but also by other cells of the immune system, such as T lymphocytes and neutrophils [9]. TNF- α participates in the regulation of the inflammatory response, attracting immune cells to sites of infection and inflammation, enhancing the production of other pro-inflammatory cytokines, and increasing vascular permeability, which allows immune cells to enter damaged tissues.

TNF- α has a powerful effect on the process of apoptosis, activating mechanisms of programmed cell death. This is important for controlling cell growth and eliminating damaged or infected cells.

Analysis of the results showed that in patients with mild hepatitis A in group 1, the level of TNF- α increased on average to 48.93 ± 1.45 pg/ml, which was more than 2.4 times higher than in the control group (20.60 ± 1.23 pg/ml) ($P < 0.001$). The median (Me) of TNF- α also increased significantly to 49.29 pg/ml, which indicates a clear manifestation of the inflammatory process even in mild hepatitis A. In patients with moderate HF, the TNF- α level was significantly elevated in group 2, reaching 64.00 ± 2.21 pg/ml, which was 3.1 times higher than in the control group ($P < 0.001$). The median (Me) was 66.39 pg/ml, indicating a developed inflammatory response. The highest TNF- α elevation was observed in patients with severe HF, in which its level reached 97.59 ± 3.11 pg/ml, which was 4.7 times higher than in the control group (20.60 ± 1.23 pg/ml, $P < 0.001$). In our study, we next examined serum HGF levels in patients with ACS before the start of treatment, and compared them with a control group (Figure 1). The data presented in Figure 1 show the serum HGF levels before treatment in patients with ACS of different severity, as well as a comparison with the control group. In the control group consisting of healthy individuals, the mean HGF level was

259.67 ± 22.20 pg/ml, the median (Me) was 232.31 pg/ml, and the individual interval was from 131.72 pg/ml to 449.17 pg/ml. Serum levels of HGF were significantly higher in patients with mild ACS: the mean level was 450.32 ± 20.59 pg/ml, which was 1.73 times higher than in the control group (P<0.001), and the mean was 468.31 pg/ml, with a range of 204.84 pg/ml to 635.87 pg/ml.

Table 1

Serum levels of studied markers before treatment in patients in the observation group

Indicators	M±m, pg/ml	Me [Q1; Q3]	Min, pg/ml	Max, pg/ml
Control group, n=21				
TNFα	20,60±1,23	19,74 [17,15; 24,74]	11,47	32,48
HGF	259,67±22,20	232,31 [221,92; 327,82]	131,72	449,17
Group 1 (light form of VGA), n=35				
TNFα	48,93±1,45***	49,29 [41,50; 57,88]	33,56	62,32
HGF	450,32±20,59***	468,31 [409,77; 539,91]	204,84	635,87
Group 2 (VGA medium heavy form), n=33				
TNFα	64,00±2,21***	66,39 [52,31; 73,61]	35,41	88,26
HGF	555,56±22,59***	574,28 [474,28; 673,26]	310,39	727,21
Group 3 (VGA heavy form), n=25				
TNFα	97,59±3,11***	97,60 [85,30; 107,51]	67,90	137,30
HGF	563,04±23,78***	589,36 [491,15; 673,26]	327,21	777,21

Note: * - "statistically significant difference when compared with the control group data (- P<0.05, ** - P<0.01, *** - P<0.001). Me - median, Q1 (percentage) - 25%, Q3 (percentage) - 75%. "* -

Figure 1. Serum HGF levels in groups of patients with ACS of varying severity before treatment.

In the group of patients with moderate ACS, HGF levels increased further, reaching 555.56 ± 22.59 pg/ml (median 574.28 pg/ml), which was 2.14 times higher than in the control group (P<0.001), with minimum values of 310.39 pg/ml and maximum values of 727.21 pg/ml. Such an increase indicates the progression of highly expressed liver damage, which requires the activation of regeneration and compensation mechanisms.

In patients with severe ACS, the mean HGF level was 563.04 ± 23.78 pg/mL (median 589.36 pg/mL) (P<0.001), with a range of 327.21 pg/mL to 777.21 pg/mL. This increase was approximately 2.17 times higher than in the control group. The next stage of our study was to determine the levels of TNF-α and HGF in serum 14 days after standard and complex treatment. The results obtained after 14 days of standard and complex treatment are presented in Table 2 below.

The data presented in Table 2 show that in patients with severe ACS, changes in serum TNF-α and HGF levels were detected after 14 days of treatment. According to the analysis of the results, statistically significant changes were detected only in TNF-α. Although the level of cachexin decreased by approximately 10% compared to baseline in both therapeutic approaches, it was still significantly higher than

in the control group, indicating that an active inflammatory process was ongoing.

Table 2

Post-treatment quantification of serum immunological parameters in a group of patients with severe VGA

Indicators	M±m, pg/ml	Me [Q1; Q3]	Min pg/ml	Max pg/ml
Control group, n=21				
TNFα	20,60±1,23	19,74 [17,15; 24,74]	11,47	32,48
HGF	259,67±22,20	232,31 [221,92; 327,82]	131,72	449,17
Group 3 (VGA heavy form), n=25				
TNFα	97,59±3,11	97,60 [85,30; 107,51]	67,90	137,30
HGF	563,04±23,78	589,360[491,15; 673,26]	327,21	777,21
Standard therapy is VGA, n=13				
TNFα	90,72±2,06*	93,29 [85,30; 97,33]	76,52	98,16
HGF	537,92±21,49^	549,36 [457,51; 605,71]	407,21	643,26
Complex therapy VGA, n=12				
TNFα	87,27±2,67**	88,38 [82,35; 95,13]	67,93	97,91
HGF	504,59±27,34^	543,87 [416,39; 580,00]	344,57	612,64

Note: * – significant when compared with the control group data ($P < 0.05$), ** – significant when compared with the control group data ($P < 0.01$), *** – very significant when compared with the control group data ($P < 0.001$). Me – median, Q1 (percentile) – 25%, Q3 (percentile) – 75%. ^ – not significant when compared with the baseline ($P > 0.05$).

Also, after standard therapy, serum TNF- α levels decreased by an average of 90.72 ± 2.06 pg/ml ($P < 0.05$), median (Me) 93.29 pg/ml, individual range 76.52–98.16 pg/ml. This indicates a decrease in inflammation, but not a significant decrease.

In combination therapy, the level of TNF- α decreased by an average of 87.27 ± 2.67 pg/ml ($P < 0.01$), median (Me) 88.38 pg/ml, individual range 67.93–97.91 pg/ml. This also indicated a moderate decrease in inflammation compared to baseline.

Discussion. In our study, we systematically analyzed the changes in the levels of immunological markers - TNF- α and HGF - in patients with viral hepatitis A, depending on the severity of the disease and the type of treatment used. The results of the analysis showed that at all levels of severity of HVA, serum TNF- α was significantly increased compared to the control group, which confirms the high activity of the inflammatory process. In our study, the highest levels of TNF- α were detected in severe forms of AHA, indicating a high degree of inflammation and damage in liver tissues. At the same time, the level of HGF, which reflects liver regeneration, also increased in moderate and severe forms of AHA, reflecting the body's adaptive mechanisms aimed at compensating for hepatocyte damage.

After 14 days of treatment, the decrease in TNF- α and HGF levels was more pronounced in patients receiving complex therapy, which demonstrated its effectiveness in reducing the inflammatory response and supporting liver regenerative processes. Importantly, complex therapy allowed to significantly reduce TNF- α levels compared to standard therapy, which is explained by the effect of additional components aimed at regulating the immune response. These results show the promise of a complex therapy approach to VGA, especially in moderate and severe cases, as more intensive support for the immune system and liver regenerative processes is required.

Summary. Thus, the results of the study demonstrate the importance of monitoring TNF- α and HGF levels in assessing the severity of the course of ACS and the effectiveness of therapy. The results also emphasize the urgency of developing and implementing integrated therapeutic approaches aimed at improving clinical outcomes and accelerating patient recovery.

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